

IMIDOCHLORIDES. PART IX. REACTION OF AROMATIC ANILIDE
IMIDOCHLORIDES WITH ETHYL SODIOACETOACETATE: SYNTHESIS
OF SOME 4-HYDROXY-2-ARYL-3-ACETYLQUINOLINES

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Desai and Shah (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 121) achieved the synthesis of otherwise inaccessible 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinolines by the condensation of benzanilide imidochlorides with ethyl sodioacetoacetate. In extension of this work imidochlorides derived from simple anilides of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-toluic acids, *m*-, *p*-bromobenzoic acids, *p*-chlorobenzoic acid, α - and β -naphthoic acids have been condensed with ethyl sodioacetoacetate, and the crude condensation products obtained were cyclised to the corresponding 4-hydroxy-2-aryl-3-acetylquinolines.

Desai and Shah's condensation of benzanilide imidochloride with ethyl sodioacetoacetate has led to the synthesis of the hitherto unknown 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline (Desai and Shah, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 121). The synthesis appears to be general as imidochlorides derived from the benzoyl derivatives of mono-substituted anilines and also of α - and β -naphthylamines condense with ethyl sodioacetoacetate affording ultimately the corresponding 4-hydroxy-2-aryl-3-acetylquinolines (Desai and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

In extension of the above work, imidochlorides derived from the simple anilides of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-toluic acids, *m*- and *p*-bromobenzoic acids, *p*-chlorobenzoic acid, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids and α - and β -naphthoic acids have been condensed with ethyl sodioacetoacetate. The condensation was carried out under the conditions of Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*). The condensation products could not be crystallised and were directly cyclised by heating under reduced pressure, when the corresponding 4-hydroxy-2-aryl-3-acetylquinolines (I, R = aryl), viz., 4-hydroxy-2-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-tolyl-3-acetyl-; 4-hydroxy-2-*m*- and *p*-bromophenyl-3-acetyl-; 4-hydroxy-2-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-acetyl-; and 4-hydroxy-2- α - and β -naphthyl-3-acetylquinolines respectively were obtained, all of which are new. The crude condensation products obtained from *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzanilide imidochlorides could be cyclised neither by heating under reduced pressure nor by heating them in diphenyl ether solution (*vide infra*).

The present investigation shows that the presence of a substituent in the acid part of the molecule does not appreciably affect either its condensation with ethyl sodioacetoacetate or the cyclisation of the crude condensation product to the quinoline derivative, thereby showing the general applicability of the synthesis.

The quinoline derivatives obtained are sparingly soluble substance with high melting points. They dissolve in dilute alkali giving yellow solutions, and do not give any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. They do not absorb bromine readily from the solution, probably due to keto-enol tautomerism of the type exhibited by 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline (cf. Heeramaneck and Shah, *Proc. Ind Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 5A, 443), as shown below.

Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*) cyclised the crude condensation products by heating under reduced pressure. In an attempt to seek alternative methods for ring-closure the condensation product of benzanilide imidochloride and ethyl sodioacetoacetate was treated with different dehydrating agents like phosphorus oxychloride, phosphorus pentoxide in xylene, concentrated sulphuric acid (97%), chlorosulphonic acid and fuming sulphuric acid, but without success. However, when the condensation product was refluxed in diphenyl ether solution for about half an hour, the cyclisation could be effected. This observation suggests an alternative method for cyclisation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The condensations of the imidochlorides with ethyl sodioacetoacetate were carried out by the method of Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*). The following compounds were prepared by this method and the cyclisation was generally effected by heating the crude condensation product under reduced pressure (usually 10 mm.) in an oil bath at 200°. The quinoline derivatives are characterised by their low solubility in common organic solvents, particularly ether, in which they are almost insoluble. They were crystallised from glacial acetic acid except as otherwise mentioned. They give yellow solutions with dilute alkali and do not give any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The yields of the quinoline derivatives are calculated on the weight of the imidochloride employed. In no case did attempts to isolate the intermediate condensation product in pure state prove fruitful.

4-Hydroxy-2-*o*-tolyl-3-acetylquinoline was obtained from *o*-toluanilide imidochloride (b. p. 197°-203°/30 mm., Kulkarni and Shah, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 171) as colorless needles, m. p. 251-52°, 10% yield. (Found: N, 5.3. C₁₈H₁₆O₂ N requires N, 5.0 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as orange needles, m. p. 292°. (Found: N, 16.0. C₂₄H₁₆O₆ N₆ requires N, 15.4 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-m-tolyl-3-acetylquinoline was prepared from *m*-toluanilide imidochloride in 10% yield (b. p. 185°-195°/8 mm. and 183°-188°/4 mm., Kulkarni and Shah, *loc. cit.*), as colorless needles m.p. 279-80°. (Found : N, 5.4. C₁₈H₁₅O₂N requires N, 5.0 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones was obtained as orange coloured needles, m. p. 297°. (Found : N, 15.6. C₂₄H₁₀O₅ N₆ requires N, 15.4 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-p-tolyl-3-acetylquinoline was prepared in 12% yield from *p*-toluanilide imidochloride (b. p. 207°/24 mm., Kulkarni and Shah, *loc. cit.*) as colorless needles. m.p. above 297°. (Found : N, 5.1. C₁₈H₁₅O₂N requires N, 5.0 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones, m.p. above 300°. (Found : N, 15.2. C₂₄H₁₀O₅ N₆ requires N, 15.4 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-m-bromophenyl-3-acetylquinoline was prepared in 13% yield from *m*-bromobenzanilide imidochloride (b. p. 250°-260°/60 mm., Kulkarni and Shah, *loc. cit.*), m. p. 257-59°. (Found : N, 4.2. C₁₇H₁₂O₂NBr requires N, 4.1 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones was obtained as orange needles, m. p. 296-97° (decomp.). (Found : N, 13.6. C₂₃H₁₀O₅ N₆ Br requires N, 13.5 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-p-bromophenyl-3-acetylquinoline was prepared in 5% yield from *p*-bromobenzanilide imidochloride (Shah and Chaubal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 652) and crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m. p. 280-82°. (Found : N, 4.2. C₁₇H₁₂O₂NBr requires N, 4.1 per cent).

p-Chlorobenzanilide Imidochloride.—Dry *p*-chlorobenzanilide (10 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (10 g.) were intimately mixed and heated on a water-bath till the evolution of hydrochloric acid ceased. The hot clear liquid was poured in about 30 c.c. of sodium-dried petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°), cooled externally by ice. The precipitated *p-chlorobenzanilide imidochloride* was quickly filtered through dry funnel, washed thoroughly with petroleum ether and dried in vacuum, m. p. 63-65°, yield 7 g. [Found : Cl, 14.1 (Shah's method, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1936, 5, 62). C₁₃H₉NCl₂ requires Cl of imidochloride, 14.2 per cent].

The imidochloride can also be isolated by crystallising the residue obtained after distillation of phosphorus oxychloride under reduced pressure, from excess of petroleum ether. The imidochloride is readily soluble in common organic solvents. It was characterised by preparation of amidine derivative by the modified method of Shah (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1924, 7, 219) as given below.

N : N'-Diphenyl-p-chlorobenzamidine.—The imidochloride (2 g.) was slowly added to a mixture of diethylaniline (4 g.) and aniline (1.5 g.) and the whole heated in an oil bath at 130°-140° for 2 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) so as to obtain the sparingly soluble hydrochloride which on trituration with ammonia and ethyl alcohol afforded the *N : N'*-diphenyl-*p*-chlorobenzamidine, crystallising from ethyl alcohol, m. p. 149°. (Found : N, 9.3. Calc. for C₁₉H₁₅N₂Cl : N, 9.1 per cent). Bharucha and Shah (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1949, 17, v, 76) give m.p. 148-50°.

4-Hydroxy-2-p-chlorophenyl-3-acetylquinoline was prepared in 15% yield from *p*-chlorobenzanilide imidochloride as colorless needles, m. p. 284°. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ NCl requires N, 4.7 per cent).

α-Naphthanilide imidochloride was prepared in the same way as *p*-chlorobenzanilide imidochloride from *α*-naphthanilide (10 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (9 g.), m. p. 94-96°, yield 7.5 g. (Found: Cl, 13.5. $C_{17}H_{12}NCl$ requires Cl, 13.4 per cent).

✓N: *N'*-*Diphenyl-α-naphthamidine* was prepared as above, m. p. 185°. Bosscheck (Ber., 1883, 16, 642) gives m. p. 183-85°.

4-Hydroxy-2-α-naphthyl-3-acetylquinoline was prepared in 15% yield from *α*-naphthanilide imidochloride and crystallised from ethyl alcohol as tiny cream-coloured needles, m. p. 232-33°. (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{21}H_{15}O_2$ N requires N, 4.5 per cent).

Methyl ether, m. p. 161-62° (Found: N, 4.3. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2$ N requires N, 4.3 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-β-naphthyl-3-acetylquinoline was prepared in 25% yield from *β*-naphthanilide imidochloride (Shah and Chaubal, loc. cit.), and crystallised from ethyl alcohol as colorless needles, m. p. 273-74°. (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{21}H_{15}O_2$ N requires N, 4.5 per cent).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. above 304°. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{27}H_{17}O_5$ N₃ requires N, 14.1 per cent).

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